

NANOMOTOR PROJECT

Tursunova Zukhra Botirovna

University of Tashkent for Applied Sciences, Gavhar Str. 1,
Tashkent 100149, Uzbekistan
mirmoh@mail.ru

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Abstract. Imagining the next developments in nanotechnology and NEMS without effective nanoscale actuators is challenging. Currently, numerous nanoactuator projects with various applications are being developed and pursued, driving advancements in production.

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Placement of the Problem. AT is a phase-based rotating NanoActivator. The AT Phase is a natural enzyme found in various organisms, serving to break down proteins, fats, and carbohydrates for digestion.

Results and Examples. The AT Phase consists of hydrophobic (water-repellent) and hydrophilic (water-attracting) parts, which are responsible for the synthesis and hydrolysis of AT. During the synthesis or hydrolysis of AT, a central subunit ring begins to form.

1-Figure. Central Subunit Ring Formation during AT Hydrolysis.

Now, although the reason for this rotation may not be fully understood, it is a ready-made biological nanomotor!

"American researchers have created a nanoactuator model utilizing laser beams as a source of energy, called electrostatic nanomotors. The nanomotor consists of two graphite cylinders stacked on top of each other. One of them serves as the rotor, and the other as the stator, with two electrical charges accumulated on either side of the rotor diameter. When exposed to variable laser beams, the rotor begins to rotate.

This actuator is composed of DNA molecules, with one end containing an organic molecule that absorbs light, and the other end containing a molecule that returns light. When the DNA chain is straightened, the absorbing and returning molecules separate from each other, the system illuminates, and conversely, when the DNA is coiled, it absorbs light. Researchers aim to utilize actin and myosin molecules as nanoactuators,

6-Figure. A nanomotor rotating under light influence based on DNA molecules, functioning as a nanoactuator."

which are the primary movers of living organisms. The next stage is the sarcomere model, which is the basic unit of muscle structure."

REFERENCES

[1] Suzdalev I.P. Physics and Chemistry of Nanoclusters, Nanostructures, and Nanomaterials. Moscow: Committee book." 2006 y. 592p.

[2] Gusev A.I. Nanomaterials, Nanostructures, Nanotechnologies. Moscow: PhysMathLit. 2007yr. 416p.

[3] Petrov Yu. I. Clusters and Small Particles. Moscow: Science. 1986y. 368p.

[4] "Boren K., Hoffman D. Absorption and Scattering of Light by Small Particles. Moscow: World." 1986y. 660p.

www.mno.ru

www.nanonewsnet.ru

www.nanobot.ru

www.microbot.ru

www.neuroelectronics.ru

www.cbio.ru

www.roboclub.ru

www.aicommunity.org

www.mno.ru/books/laz.php

www.mno.ru/books/eoc/eoc.php

www.prognosis.org.ua